

Make QoS Look Easy with Segment Routing

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Anonymous Author(s)

ABSTRACT

With the growth of demand for quasi instantaneous communication services such as augmented and virtual reality, real-time video streaming, gaming, and industry 4.0 applications, multi-constraint Traffic Engineering (TE) becomes increasingly important. While previous TE management planes have proven laborious to deploy, Segment Routing (SR), a new flexible architecture, revived interest in practical solutions for the Multi-Constraint Optimal Paths problem (MCOP). MCOP is computationally intensive when dealing with two or more additive metrics. However, this difficulty is often misinterpreted as its complexity is actually polynomial in the numeric value of the input.

While efficiently solving MCOP is still challenging without relying on approximations, we first leverage practical aspects of SR; an operational constraint added by its deployment. Each path is translated into a list of segments that should not exceed a certain length. This length represents the number of segments that a router can impose on each packet at line-rate. In practice, this apparent extra-complexity drastically reduces the solution space. Besides SR, we also leverage real network characteristics (the spreading of one of the metrics in particular) to design BEST2COP, an efficient but exact algorithm dealing with two metrics in addition to the operational constraint. BEST2COP provides optimal solutions for all kinds of SR networks ranging from worst cases to (favorable) realistic networks. For such networks, BEST2COP returns all the constrained TE paths for up to thousands of destinations in way less than a second.

1 INTRODUCTION

What is a best path? This fundamental routing question has multiple answers. Usually, for best-effort traffic, Internet Service Providers (ISP) rely on a single additive metric based on a cost function applied on each link in the Intradomain Gateway Protocol (IGP), such as OSPF or IS-IS.

However, specific traffic like large (aggregate of) real-time flows have strong requirements, across multiple dimensions. A single metric, even hybrid, is not able to capture the full set of properties necessary for an ISP and its customers. For real-time services, multiple weights can be advertised

for each link within the IGP and Quality of Service (QoS) routing [29] is then required to find the best *constrained path*, *i.e.*, a path satisfying the given QoS constraint(s) on one or several metrics and that may optimizes another. Such QoS constraints can be of different nature and relate to metrics such as the bandwidth, the jitter or the propagation delay. In addition to the performance guarantees, ISP often aim to minimize the resource usage in their network, *i.e.*, the IGP cost. This leads to the optimization variant of the constraints path problem, which we aim to solve. Among the constrained paths, one can look for the path minimizing the IGP cost.

1.1 MCOP Multi-Constraint Optimal Paths

The general problem is referred to as MCOP (Multi Constrained Optimal Paths). A specific case of MCOP closer to ours, DCLC (Delay Constrained Least Cost), considering only two given additive metrics (referred to as M1 and M2 in this paper), has attracted a lot of attention from the research community [24]. In practice, and in the following, we will consider M1 as the IGP cost and M2 as the propagation delay (they are the most popular metrics).

DCLC, though less general than MCOP, is known to be related to the set of NP-complete decision problems [35]. Indeed, when dealing with multi-dimensional weights, any path better on at least one metric compared to current best known paths may be interesting. These paths are referred to as *non-dominated* paths and make up the *pareto front* of the solution. To solve DCLC exactly, the whole pareto front of the solution (2-dimensional when considering two metrics) must be explored. Since the latter may grow exponentially, these problems are considered intractable. While the optimization variant makes our problem NP-hard in theory, it is also known that problematic cases are not likely to occur in practice [5, 25] thanks to networks' structures and limited nature of their metrics.

In this paper, we go further than heuristics and bring guarantees even for complex cases as long as they verify two reasonable assumptions. The problem can be solved efficiently but still exactly just looking at the technology in use and the metrics in play.

1.2 Segment Routing and MCOP

First, our work is designed for a specific Traffic-Engineering (TE) technology, Segment Routing (SR) [8, 9]. Thanks to

its scalable nature and greatly reduced management overhead regarding the previous options, SR has become the new state-of-the-art technology with growing in popularity both within the research community and with ISPs.

With SR, forwarding paths are translated to list of segments, which can be seen as checkpoints the packet has to go through. This list is then encoded within each packet and used by routers to forward them through each checkpoint sequentially, following the best IGP path (or just one single link called adjacency). The size of the list is however limited, as only *SEGMAX* segments may be imposed on each packet for line-rate processing with today's hardware.

Our goal is then to compute lists of segments from a source towards any destination that:

- Do not require more than *SEGMAX* segments;
- Verify constraints for up to two metrics *M1* and *M2* (namely the IGP cost and the propagation delay); among these paths, we look for the ones minimizing either the number of segments (*M0*), *M1* or *M2*.

While SR fits perfectly for this usage, it may seem at first glance that the requirement to encode the path in a limited number of segments adds a layer of complexity to our already complex problem (a SR variant of DCLC). However, we are only interested in technically *SR feasible* solutions. Thus, any path that translates in more than *SEGMAX* segments is not viable and can be ignored even if it verifies the other constraints processing. This operational constraint thus drastically reduces the exploration space to our advantage and is one of the two reasons why we can claim to be efficient, and exact regarding SR feasible paths.

1.3 ISP rely on Simple enough Metric(s)

Our second important assumption is about one of the two metrics. Our algorithm is able to optimize any of the three metrics while respecting constraints on the others. However, we require either *M1* or *M2* to be bounded (having so a limited number of distinct values). While this requirement may look strong at first, we argue that most metrics already meet this requirement naturally.

Indeed, the IGP distances may very well respect this requirement, though they ultimately depend on the ISP configuration and choices. Less flexible but more constrained, the delay should naturally meet this requirement. First, a constrained path should generally meet some strict constraints regarding its delay, typically < 100ms, usually closer to 10 or even 2ms. In addition, no delay measurement can be claimed to be exact, *i.e.*, true (or perfectly accurate). ISPs are aware that measured delays (usually measured with MPLS PM [10] or OWAMP [28]/TWAMP [18]) have a limited *trueness* (as defined in ISO 5725-1 [20]) or accuracy, even with efficient

hardware PTP timestamping systems, *i.e.*, overall, an acceptable error of at worst 0.1ms per link seems to be a sufficient tradeoff that can accommodate all worst cases (e.g. long congested links or overloaded devices leading to a biased measurement of the actual propagation delays) still with a reasonable accuracy for most networking usages, as a guarantee at the grain of a tenth of a millisecond looks enough regarding most real time requirements in general.

Thus, even though the precision of the measurements is really high, *i.e.*, nanosecond, their trueness, or accuracy, make it difficult to rank nearly delay-tied path at the sub-micro accuracy. For a constraint of 10ms, with a grain of 0.1ms, it leads to a margin error of only 0.5% if we round up the *M2* distance. This error is inherent to the measure. Due to both its variation depending on physical properties, its dependency on the clock synchronization, skew, resolution and accuracy on distributed devices [1, 2], we argue that one cannot state that a path having a measured delay of 9.95ms is truly better than a 10ms one. We leverage these characteristics: the measured delay is naturally bounded and discrete with limited number of distinct values by essence due to the limited trueness of the measurements; it allows us to store non-dominated paths in an efficient bounded structure and thus makes the worst-case complexity of our algorithm perfectly and easily predictable. As long as the weight bound does not depend exponentially on the network dimensions, the problem remains polynomial to solve but can be still remain challenging for large networks.

1.4 Overview of our Contributions

Our algorithm, BEST2COP (Best Exact Segment Track for 2-Constrained Optimal Paths), takes benefit from the two previous properties. In short, it computes all the paths verifying three constraints (including the SR operational one) and optimizes one of them. BEST2COP provides exact optimal constrained TE solutions in a time period acceptable for the routing convergence, that is under the second for most if not all cases as we will experimentally show. It leverages two practical properties (*SEGMAX* and the trueness of the delay) that make the problem easier than it seem at first glance. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first TE algorithm that enables to practically deploy such a TE flavor with SR. In this context, BEST2COP provides exact solutions with efficiency guarantees at a controllable accuracy grain. Other existing algorithms are mainly heuristics or theoretical approximation framework not leveraging deterministically the ground properties of real networks. We guarantee to solve our SR variant problem exactly and efficiently as long as our assumptions about one metric apply. BEST2COP can easily check if these properties are verified (looking at the

two metric spreading), and predict the upper bound of its inherent complexity.

In Section 2, we start by formally defining the concepts and related problems that we solve throughout the paper. Once established, our notations and objects like the SR graph will allow us to properly describe our algorithm in Section 3, before extensively evaluate its performance, both regarding worst and realistic cases in Section 4. We conclude the paper discussing the related work in Section 5 and summarizing our achievements and discussion future work in Section 6.

2 FROM MCOP TO 2-CONSTRAINED SEGMENT PATHS

In this section, we formally introduce and define all notations and concepts used to design BEST2COP. More precisely, we detail the construct we use to encompass Segment Routing, called the *SR graph*, and how this object and the characteristics of ISP networks are used to our advantage.

2.1 The Need for an SR Graph

As stated, BEST2COP is designed for SR, which embeds segments (routing instructions) that translates to a specific path, within each packet. Segments are interpreted in sequence by the routers to make the packet follow the paths described.

SR may use *node segments* and *adjacency segments*. A node segment v is interpreted by a router u as *forward the packet to v through the best IGP path(s)*. An adjacency segment indicates that the packet should be forwarded to a direct neighbor v through a specific interface

We thus need to be aware of the number of segments we are using when looking for a path (to not exceed SEGMAX), as well as the IGP cost and delay of the paths encoded by each segment to not exceed M1 or M2. To do so, we gather this information in the *SR graph*. An SR graph represents the segments as edges. The weights of these edges are thus the weights of the path encoded by the segment. For example, a node segment v allows to forward a packet from u to v through the best IGP path(s). It is thus translated as a link (u, v) within the SR graph, whose weight is equal to the weight of the best IGP path(s) between u and v . An adjacency segment, on the other hand, is translated as an edge (u, v) whose weight is equal to the link of the interface the packet will be forwarded through on the original graph. Any path from u to v that can be encoded by a single segment will be translated as an edge between u and v on the SR graph. Consequently, a path requiring x segments can be represented as a path of x edges in the SR graph (agnostically to its actual length in the original, non-transformed graph).

This transformation, though simple when considering only the IGP cost, becomes more subtle when dealing with

multiple metrics. We will detail more formally this transformation and show how the performances of our algorithm are made possible via a formal description and analysis of the SR weights. Hence, we first describe the SR graph construction.

2.2 The SR Graph Construction

We use Figures 1 and 2 to illustrate the SR-graph construction throughout this section. We start by describing the notations we use to describe the original graphs.

Let us denote G the graph of the original topology. $G = (V, E)$, where V and E respectively refer to the set of vertices and edges. As G can have multiple parallel links between a pair (u, v) , we use $E(u, v)$ to denote all the direct links between nodes u and v . We consider two valuation functions $w1_G$ and $w2_G$ that return for each link l in E the link weight for both metrics, M1 and M2, respectively. Recall that we consider here that M1 refers to the IGP-cost of a link, and M2 refers to its delay. The distance $(d1_G(P), d2_G(P))$ of a path P is simply the sum of the weights of the edges it contains:

$$\forall i = 1, 2 \quad di_G(P) = \sum_{l \in P} wi_G(l)$$

For instance, in Figure 1, there are two edges between nodes N and S , so $E(N, S) = \{l_{NS1}, l_{NS2}\}$ where both links have an IGP-cost of 1 ($w1_G(l_{NS1}) = w1_G(l_{NS2}) = 1$), and a delay of resp. $w2_G(l_{NS1}) = 1.12$ and $w2_G(l_{NS2}) = 1.24$.

We can now formally describe the transformation of G to an SR graph. From the graph G , representing the network topology, we create a transformed multigraph: the SR graph denoted $G' = (V, E')$. While the set of nodes in G' is the same as in G , the set of edges differs. More precisely, an edge $l = (u, v) \in E'$ represents either a *node segment*, a set of ECMP best paths in G between nodes u and v ; or an *adjacency segment*: a direct link in E if l is not dominated by any segment between u and v .

More formally, let us describe the set $E'(u, v)$ of links in G' between nodes u and v . As we said, each segment in a segment list represents a checkpoint that packets should reach sequentially. By default, the route between two checkpoints used by a packet follows the ECMP load balanced best IGP paths (M1), hence there exists a link in G' between any pair of nodes (u, v) , representing all the paths between u and v that are optimal with respect to M1 and can thus be encoded through a single segment. Note that, assuming G is a connected graph (having only one connected component), then G' is a full mesh, as shown in Figure 2. Indeed, there exist a path between any two nodes u, v and thus there is always a path between them (the best IGP path) that can be encoded through a single node segment.

For instance, in Figure 1, there exist three paths from N to L which an optimal IGP-cost of 3: $N-O-L$ with distance

(3, 6.2), $N-S-L$ with distance (3, 2.3) and $N-S-L$ with distance (3, 2.4). All of them may be used when using the node segment L on N . Thus, they are represented by the link (N, L) in G' . One may notice two things. First, we do not use 6.2 as the delay value but 62. The delay can be represented as a precise floating number, but its actual trueness (or accuracy) is limited. ISPs cannot expect more than a 0.1 millisecond accuracy in the worst conditions. This implies that we can safely round the M2-weights before applying the sum when computing the M2-distance of a path without losing useful information. Thus the path from N to L using the links with the best IGP-cost (*i.e.*, the node segment) has distances $(3, 62) = (1 + 2, 40 + 22)$, where 22 is the delay 2.15ms times 10 rounded up at the 0.05 accuracy. As we will detail later in this section, this in turn reduces the complexity of our problem. Second, we chose 62 as the delay of the node segment. Indeed, we tune the SR transformation to be able to deal with multiple metrics. When using a node segment, the packet may be load-balanced across all best paths, we can only guarantee that the delay will not be more than the worst delay of all the ECMP paths, *i.e.*, 62 in this case.

This observation implies that $E'(u, v)$ contains exactly one *node segment* $l_{ns}(u, v)$ (the black edges in Fig. 2) that represents the whole set $P_G(u, v)$ of best paths, regarding the M1-distance, from u to v in G . The M1-weight $w1(l_{ns}(u, v))$ is the common M1-distance of the paths in $P_G(u, v)$ and the M2-weight $w2(l_{ns}(u, v))$ is defined as the maximum M2-distance among all the paths in $P_G(u, v)$. Thus, link representing node segments in G' verify the following:

$$\begin{aligned} w1(l_{ns}(u, v)) &= d1_G(P) \quad \text{for any } P \in P_G(u, v) \\ w2(l_{ns}(u, v)) &= \max_{P \in P_G(u, v)} d2_G(P) \end{aligned}$$

In addition to this unique node segment, $E'(u, v)$ can contain other *adjacency segments* (blue edges in Fig. 2).

An adjacency segment corresponds exactly to an edge in the graph G and forces the packet to go through a specific link. Note that if the best IGP path has both a better delay and a better cost than the considered link, there is no point in using an adjacency segment, a node segment being sufficient. Thus, an edge $l \in E(u, v)$ is also in $E'(u, v)$ only if it is not dominated by the node segment, *i.e.*, if $w1_G(l) \geq w1(l_{ns}(u, v))$ and $w2_G(l) < w2(l_{ns}(u, v))$, or by any other non-dominated adjacency segments. The M1-weight $w1(l)$, resp. M2-weight, of an adjacency segment is exactly the M1-weight $w1_G(l)$, resp. M2-weight, of its corresponding link in G . For example, in Figure 1, the best path from N to O has a weight of (1, 4) and is translated to the node segment of the same weight in Figure 2 as a link. However, there is another direct link between both nodes with a lower delay (2, 3.9). Since it is not dominated by the node segment, we add an adjacency segment (2, 39) to G' so that we are able to use the corresponding link. Once again, we round the

Figure 1: Raw network graph: $G(V, E)$

delay to the 0.5 accuracy. Notice that it is not possible that $w1_G(l) < d1(l_{ns}(u, v))$, as otherwise paths in $l_{ns}(u, v)$ would not have the best M1-distance. A link in G may be part of the set of ECMP paths towards v . In this case, it is translated to an adjacency segment and keeps its M2-distance if the latter is better than the maximum M2 of the ECMP paths.

For example, in Figure 1, there are two ECMP paths from L to M , with weight (8, 1.10) and (8, 4.7). We thus translate the node segment to a link with weight (8, 47) in G' . However, the edge (L, M) possesses a better delay than the node segment and may thus be useful. It is thus translated to an adjacency segment in G' as a link with weight (8, 11). When routing packets from L to M , one can either use the adjacency segment to use the specific link with lower delay, or use the node segment (and ECMP paths) towards M .

The SR graph G' can be built for all sources and destinations thanks to an APSP algorithm (like applying $|V|$ Dijkstra or Floyd and Warshall algorithms) to deduce the weight of each node segments. We will consider this SR construction as a shared input for BEST2COP among all possible sources in V (while our algorithm is performed from each source as explained in the next section). Note that this transformation, inherent to SR, leads to a complexity of $O(|V| \times (|V| \log(|V|) + |E|))$. Since this transformation is needed by SR, we do not take it into account when evaluating our algorithm, whose complexity will not exceed the one just mentioned.

2.3 ISP Characteristics Used to our Advantage in the SR Graph

In this section we explain how the characteristics of real ISP networks (*i.e.*, the technology used and the nature of their metrics) are used to our advantage and translate in the construct we have detailed in this section.

2.3.1 Simple and bounded metric(s). DCLC is pseudo-polynomial [13]. More precisely, it is polynomial in the value of the largest number present in the input after conversion to integer, *i.e.*, the maximum value taken by the input times the accuracy of the input (this product is denoted \mathcal{S} in the next subsection). Consequently, having only one bounded metric among M1 or M2 makes our problem polynomial. The

Figure 2: SR network graph: $G'(V, E')$

problem’s complexity is even more simple if the accuracy of the bounded metric is coarse enough. There are two ways M1 or M2 can possess these properties and greatly reduce the problem’s complexity. First, the metric can be bounded, and/or its accuracy coarse by nature (inherently to its origin). Second, if the maximum constraint in use is small, it also bounds the corresponding metric quite drastically, as edges (resp. segment paths) with weights (resp. distances) greater than the constraint can be ignored when exploring G' .

Our solution can look and adapt to the most suited metric automatically. However, we argue that M2, the propagation delay, is the best candidate and will, most of the time, have the lower numerical value S by design. Indeed, while the IGP cost is bounded due to its representation in memory, backup link have a high IGP cost that can considerably increase the range (and thus the bound) of the metric if manually tuned. The IGP-cost is also rarely constrained in most practical usecases, ISP are interested in the best IGP path (*i.e.*, M1 is minimized, not constrained as with DCLC). In addition, the IGP cost can be encoded with a quite high integer input (up to 24bits with IS-IS), and can not be rounded, as, by design, its relevance depend on the ISP configuration (not all weights are automatically configured). In some situations, a difference of 1 in the IGP cost may produce an effect desired by its operators.

The delay on the other hand, is usually always constrained through a strict bound (always lower than 100ms in practical cases). In addition, the delay of a path can be represented by a precise number in memory but the trueness (or accuracy) of the measured delay of an edge in the graph G is not the same as the precision in memory. For instance, the typical trueness of the delay can be set to 0.1ms, which means that floating number can be rounded to integer taking 0.1ms as unit. Since is delay is bounded through its constraints, and since its precision is brought down by the inherent lack of accuracy of measurements, it is most likely to always have a

limited numerical value, and is thus the metric we will focus on to reduce our problem’s complexity in practice.

2.3.2 *Segment Routing and SEGMAX.* The constraint on the number of segments is another property we leverage and that combines with the inherent limitation of at least one metric. Paths in the SR graph G' (*i.e.*, list of segments) cannot contain more than SEGMAX, or c_0 segments (around 10 in practice). This constraint on the metric M0 (representing the number of segment) is used to make our algorithm only explore feasible SR paths, *i.e.*, of less than SEGMAX segments. When using the SR graph, this is equivalent to only explore paths of less than SEGMAX hops. In addition to limiting the exploration space, this property also bounds the maximum distance of a feasible segment path on M1 and M2. Regardless of the constraint c_j we know that an SR path will not exceed an M_j -distance of the maximum w_j weight on the SR graph times SEGMAX. More formally, let us denote S_1 , resp. S_2 , the numerical value (*i.e.*, the maximum weight relying on integers) of metric M1, resp. M2, in the SR graph G' . We know that a feasible SR paths has a weight of at most $SEGMAX \times S_j$ (with $j = 1, 2$). Moreover, note that weights and distances exceeding the constraint can be respectively removed (pruning of some edges) and ignored.

Thus, the M_j -weight of a path in G' is bounded by Γ_j

$$\Gamma_j = \min(c_j \times t, SEGMAX \times S_j) \quad \text{with } j = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

With t being the level of accuracy of M_j already taken into account in the SR graph weights (so in S_j) during the SR transformation (when rounding an turning floating values as integers). With our settings for M2, we have $t = 10$, it is the multiplying factor modelling an accuracy of 0.1ms with integers expressing ms units. This limited value is of great importance because it strongly reduces the time complexity required by our algorithm to maintain the Pareto front of all best dominating paths. Indeed, since the weights were converted to integers by taking the metrics’ trueness into consideration, we know that the M_j -weight of a path in G' may only take all the integer values from 0 to Γ_j , and thus the size of Pareto front cannot exceed $\Gamma = \min(\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2)$. Assuming $\Gamma = \Gamma_2$ to simplify (and for reasons described previously), then it is sufficient to store only the best M1-distance indexed on the respective M2 distance, leading to a Pareto front that can be stored in a static array of size Γ_2 . In other words, if only Γ values are possible for the M2 distance, there are at most Γ non-dominated pair of distances. Hence, the DCLC problem is polynomial in Γ . More generally speaking, the choice of the indexing metric J used to store the Pareto front can be computed as $J = \text{argmin}_j(\Gamma_j)$ with $c_1 = \infty$ for the DCLC problem.

2.4 The 2COP+ problem

We can now explicitly formulate the MCOP problem specifically for SR considering two metrics, namely the IGP cost (M1) and the propagation delay (M2) (and the operational M0). We present 3 problems with increasing refinements. The algorithm we propose in Section 3 solves the last problem, and a fortiori all that precede. First let us define the simpler decision problem.

Definition. *2-Constrained Paths (2CP):* Given a source $s \in V$, a constraint $c0 = SEGMAX$ on the number of segments, $c1$ on the IGP cost, and $c2$ on the propagation delay, ask the following question. For each destination n , does **there exist** a segment path (i.e., a path in G') sp_n verifying

$$\begin{aligned} d0(sp_n) &= |sp_n| \leq c0 \\ d1(sp_n) &\leq c1, d2(sp_n) \leq c2 \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

As we said, this problem is NP-complete in general but is polynomial in Γ . In practice, the constraint $c1$ will be infinite, as discussed in the previous sections with DCLC, and the constraint $c2$ will not be too large to fit applications requirements for low delay communications leading to a small enough Γ to limit the time complexity. So solutions with practically efficient computation times exists to solve this problem. We denote by $FP(c0, c1, c2, n)$ the set of *feasible paths* towards node n that verifies the three constraints (including the operational one on $c0 = SEGMAX$).

For instance, in the graph G' illustrated in Figure 2, with node S as the source, we have

$$\begin{aligned} FP(3, \infty, 70, D) &= \{S-L-D(6, 46), S-N-O-D(4, 65), \\ &S-N-O-D(4, 66), S-N-O-D(5, 64) S-N-O-D(5, 65), \\ &S-L-O-D(6, 46), S-L-M-D(14, 34), S-L-M-D(14, 70)\} \end{aligned}$$

where the four $S-N-O-D$ segments differ on the kind of link they use, node segment or adjacency segment. For instance, $S-N-O-D(4, 65)$ and $S-N-O-D(5, 64)$ differ by the use of an adjacency segment instead of a node segment to reach N from O .

An algorithm solving only the 2CP problem does not need to visit or return the whole FP set: it stops and returns True as soon as one constrained path is found for each destination (False, otherwise). However, our algorithm will look for most interesting paths among them, and store (and extend) non dominated ones to be able to minimize any metric (including M0 with our last problem). This ability to efficiently visit the whole Pareto front along with its three dimensions (M0, M1 and M2) while returning a subset of optimal segment paths regarding one of the metric, will allow us to solve the two optimization problems described below.

Definition. *2-Constrained Optimal Paths (2COP):* Given a source $s \in V$ and the same constraints as 2CP, 2COP consists

in finding, for each destination n , a segment path verifying all the constraints and **optimizing one metric** $M_j, j = 1, 2$. For each destination n , we search a segment path sp_n verifying

$$\begin{aligned} sp_n &\in FP(c0, c1, c2, n) \\ \forall sp' \in FP(c0, c1, c2, n), & dj(sp_n) \leq dj(sp') \end{aligned}$$

If several paths exist, we consider only the one that are not dominated. \blacksquare

Actually, a path optimizing one metric is necessarily a non dominated path. As a general illustration of this new problem, using S as source, and denoting

$$2COP(SEGMAX, c1, c2, M_j, n) \in FP(SEGMAX, c1, c2, n)$$

as the best 2-constrained paths for metric M_j , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} 2COP(3, \infty, 70, M1, D) &= S-N-O-D(4, 65) \\ 2COP(3, \infty, 70, M2, D) &= S-L-M-D(14, 34) \end{aligned}$$

Notice that the path $S-N-O-D(4, 66)$ is also optimal for M1, but it is dominated by $S-N-O-D(4, 65)$, hence only the non-dominated one is considered. Also, observe that the results are not the same according to the optimized metric. As one can see, the path minimizing M1 is here different that the one minimizing M2. Our algorithm is able to return each of these solutions. At the last iteration of BEST2COP, they are the first element and respectively the last element of the list storing the final pareto front. However, as already discussed, we can claim for even more and be adaptative and flexible regarding constraints and optimization strategies: we can collect, over the i iterations, the whole three-dimensional pareto front, and can thus envision to be more versatile and so solve what we called the 2COP+ problem, a more general extension.

Indeed, the constraint $c2$ can be chosen large enough by the operator to ensure that solutions exist. Among all the solutions, other optimization or constraint objectives can apply. For instance, one may want to obtain a segment path that minimizes first the delay and then the IGP-cost, or first the segment counter (M0) and then another one. In addition, we aim to handle variable usecases: a customer may change its needs after the execution of our algorithm. In particular, one may wish for a smaller constraint $c2' < c2$ on M2 if some requirements become stricter. Our algorithm does not need to be re-run in order to find the new updated optimal constrained path. Finally, ISPs could be interested to find destination-specific constraints and optimizations. That is having heterogeneous constraints (in particular on $c2$) and strategies across destination-based flows.

From those observations we refine the 2COP problem. The 2COP+ problem is more complex but more useful in practice as one computation gives enough information to accommodate flows with variable and heterogeneous constraints: basically our algorithm returns and structures the entire pareto

front considering large virtual constraints (pseudo-infinite) to solve the 2COP+ problem in a very general way.

Definition. *2COP+*: Given a source $s \in V$, the same constraints as 2CP, the 2-constrained optimal segment paths with parameterized solutions consists in finding a function $f(n, c0', c1', c2', Mj)$ for each destination n , for all **stricter sub-constraints** $ck' \leq ck$, $k = 0, 1, 2$, that returns, if it exists, a segment path towards n verifying all ck' and optimizing any metric Mj , $j = 0, 1, 2$. Again, if several solution exists, we only consider the non-dominated ones.■

Notice that the image set of f (all the possible outputs) corresponds to the three-dimensional pareto front. Indeed, any feasible path in $FP(c0, c1, c2, n)$ with distance (a, b, c) that is not dominated is the output of $f(n, a, b, c, Mj)$, for any $j = 0, 1, 2$. Conversely, if $f(n, a, b, c, Mj)$ exists, then it is in the pareto front by definition.

Another way to see set of solutions of the 2COP+ problems (the image of f), is as the union of the all the possible solutions of the 2COP problem using stricter sub-constraints. Let $2COP + (c0, c1, c2, n)$ denote the set of solutions of the 2COP+ problems. We have

$$2COP+(c0, c1, c2, n) = \{2COP(c0', c1', c2', n) \mid ck' \leq ck, k=0, 1, 2\}$$

For example, referring again to Figure 2, we have

$$2COP+(3, \infty, 70, D) = \{S-L-D(6, 46), S-N-O-D(4, 65), \\ S-L-M-D(14, 34), S-N-O-D(5, 64)\}$$

Thus, to minimize M1, M2 or M0, all the solutions are present in the 2COP+ set. For example, the path respecting the constraints and minimizing M1 is $f(D, 3, \infty, 70, M1) = S-N-O-D(4, 65)$. In addition, to enforce a stricter constraint a posteriori, e.g., $c2 = 64$ instead of 70, the new results can be found in the output without re-running our algorithm. Here, the new result would be $f(D, 3, \infty, 64, M1) = S-N-O-D(5, 64)$. Similarly, if one decides to minimize M2 or M0 instead of M1, the results are already within our output. One can also minimize the number of segment and obtain $f(D, 3, \infty, 64, M0) = S-L-D(6, 46)$. Our algorithm takes the constraints and the SR graph G' as inputs and builds a data structure (an array) that can be requested to return the result of function f in constant (or at least sub-linear) time given stricter sub-constraints. In any cases, it is easier to iterate over images of f than relaunching the whole algorithm with new constraints and objectives.

3 THE BEST2COP ALGORITHM

In this section we describe in detail BEST2COP, our algorithm solving the three problems described in the previous section, 2COP+ in particular. We discuss its efficiency along with its pseudo-code and data-structures. The main procedure follows the principle of the Bellman-Ford algorithm.

Simply put, at each iteration, BEST2COP (i) extends the known non-dominated paths by one segment (*i.e.*, one edge on the SR graph). (ii) Extended paths that are on the Pareto front are then extended themselves, but not before the next iteration. Thanks to SR, these two steps only need to be done $SEGMAX = 10$ times. Indeed, since we extend path segment by segment, paths of i segments (*i.e.*, i edges in the SR graph) are explored at iteration i . Thus, all paths explored after the tenth iteration require more than $SEGMAX$ segments and can be ignored. Consequently, our algorithm iterates only tenth times and not $|V| - 1$ as it is the case at worst for Bellmann-Ford (on a raw graph).

The good performances of the algorithm are not only due to $SEGMAX$ (handled naturally with the Bellmann-Ford approach), but also to well-chosen data structures benefiting from the limits of the simplest metric, the one having the spreading, $S = \min(S_1, S_2)$ in the SR-graph G' . We consider that $S = S_2$ in the following.

Main Procedure. We start the algorithm by preparing the variables that store the results, the Pareto front, the distances of the best known paths, and the paths that can be extended. The most important variable in our algorithm is the variable `dist` which stores and filters, for each vertex, the distances of the best known paths. Since the M2-distance of any feasible path in G' is bounded by Γ we can store all the best paths to a node v in a static array `dist[v]` of size Γ where the indexes correspond to the M2-distances and the values correspond to the M1-distances (Line 1). For instance, if one of the best path towards a node v has a distance $(d1v, d2v)$, then the value $d1v$ is placed in `dist[v][d2v]`. Coupled with the bounded number of values the delay can take, as stated in Section ??, this allows us to store the entire Pareto front in a single static array, with constant access time. Initially, the values in the array `dist[n]` are assumed to be infinity.

The variable `pf` is also a static array of size $|V|$ (Line 2), that stores, for each node n , the current Pareto front as a simple list (implemented as a linked list or as an array list for efficiency) of pairs $(d1n, d2n)$. The variable `extendable` is a simple list that contains the nodes where a path can be extended, along with the distances of the best known paths towards it. For instance, later in the execution, if `extendable` contains the pair $(u, [(d1u, d2u), (d1u', d2u')])$, it means that there are two paths from the source to node u , with distance $(d1u, d2u)$ and $(d1u', d2u')$ respectively, that could be extended by adding one edge. We later refer to paths that can be extended for a given node as *d_list*.

In the initialization, we set that the only known best path at the beginning is to the source node `src` itself, and has distance $(0, 0)$, so `dist[src][0]` is set to 0 (Line 9). This trivial path can be extended, so we add $(src, [(0, 0)])$ to `extendable` (Line 10), and is in the Pareto front of `src` (Line 11). After

the initialization, the main loop starts. For each iteration, we perform two actions. First, we extend all the extendable paths (Line 14) by one edge. These new paths may be on the Pareto front, or they may be dominated. This verification is performed later. For now, we consider that these paths may be on the Pareto front, and thus store them in `pf_cand`. Then we compute the new Pareto front (that takes into account the newly discovered paths), and the new paths to extend at the next iteration (*i.e.*, paths on the Pareto front that were just discovered) (Line 15), using the previous Pareto front and the new Pareto front candidates.

Algorithm 1: BEST2COP

```

1 results := Array of size |V|
2 pfront := Array of size |V|
3 dist := Array of size |V|
4 extendable := []
5 forall n ∈ V do
6   results[n] := Array of size SEGMAX
7   pfront[n] = []
8   dist[n] := Array of size Γ
9 dist[src][0] = 0
10 add(extendable, (src, [(0,0)]))
11 add(pfront[src], 0)
12 i = 1
   // End init
13 while extendable ≠ [] and i ≤ SEGMAX do
14   pf_cand, dist = ExtendPaths (
15     extendable, dist)
16   extendable, pfront = ComputeExtendable (
17     pf_cand, pfront, dist, i)
18   forall n ∈ V | pfront[n] ≠ [] do
19     results[n][i-1] = pfront[n]
20   i = i + 1
21 return results

```

Algorithm 2: ExtendPaths

```

1 pf_cand := Array of size |V|
2 forall (u, d_list) ∈ extendable do
3   forall v ∈ succ(u) do
4     forall l ∈ E'(u,v) do
5       forall (d1u, d2u) ∈ d_list do
6         d1v = d1u + w1(l)
7         d2v = d2u + w2(l)
8         // Filters: constraints and distances
9         if d1v ≤ c1 and d2v ≤ c2
10        and d1v < dist[v][d2v] then
11          dist[v][d2v] = d1v
12          add(pf_cand[v], d2v)
13 return pf_cand, dist

```

At the end of the iteration, the best known paths were extended by one edge and the distances updated. The variable `pfront` contains the Pareto front of each node (as destination) for the current iteration i , and thus the Pareto front concerning paths of i segments. We saved the Pareto front of all the nodes in our result array `results` for the current iteration. Hence, after at most `SEGMAX` iterations, `results` contains all the information we need to answer the problem `2COP+`. We now detail how the two inner procedures work.

ExtendPaths Procedure. The `ExtendPaths` procedure takes the list of extendable paths, *i.e.*, paths from the previous iteration that were on the Pareto front, and returns the extended paths and the updated array containing the best distances. These extended paths are candidate paths for the Pareto front. To compute them, for each node u that has extendable paths with distances `d_list` (Line 2), we try to extend the paths towards all successors v of u (Line 3) by adding an edge (*i.e.*, a segment). For each edge l in $E'(u, v)$ from u to v , we obtain the `M1` and `M2` distances of the extended path (a segment path of i hops) by adding the distances of the initial path (having $i - 1$ segments) to u and the weights of the edge *i.e.*, $(d1v, d2v) = (d1u + w1(l), d2u + w2(l))$, l being a node segment or an adjacency segment. If this new path respects both constraints, we check if the new path is better than the existing best known path having the same `M2`-distance (Line 9). If so, we update the distances (Line 10), otherwise we ignore this new path. If we update the best known path, we also add this new path to the potential candidates for the new Pareto front (Line 11).

Algorithm 3: ComputeExtendable

```

1 extendable = []
2 forall n ∈ V | pf_cand[n] ≠ [] do
3   d2_it = min([0..Γ-1], [0..i × S-1])
4   pfront[n] = []
5   last_d1 = ∞
6   forall d2 ∈ d2_it do
7     if dist[n][d2] < last_d1 then
8       add(pfront[n], d2)
9       last_d1 = dist[n][d2]
10  add(extendable, (n, pfront[n] ∩ pf_cand[n]))
11  pf_cand[n] = []
12 return extendable, pfront

```

ComputeExtendable procedure. This procedure checks which candidate paths actually are on the Pareto front. These paths will in turn be extended in the next iteration. Indeed, if a candidate path is not in the Pareto front for a node n , then all its possible extensions are not in the Pareto fronts of its successors and there is no point in extending it. To compute the new Pareto front of a node n , we iterate over all

the distances in $\text{dist}[u]$ to extract the Pareto front from it. Note that the new Pareto front may only contain paths from pf_cand and the old Pareto. One can thus imagine to only check the paths in $\text{pf_cand}[n] \cup \text{front}[n]$. However, with a small Γ , this optimization does not lead to a significant difference in performance.

One can see that the M2-distance of a path in the new Pareto front, after i iterations, is at most $\min(\Gamma, i \times S)$ (each edge in E' has an M2-weight of at most S). This implies that, at worst, we have to iterate over all the indexes of $\text{dist}[n]$ (from 0 to $i \times S$ or Γ at worst), to retrieve the Pareto front (iterator array created Line 3). Note that we iterate over the indexes in increasing order. Since the indexes represent the M2-distance of a path, a distance $(d1, d2)$ is in the Pareto front if $d1 = \text{dist}[u][d2]$ is strictly smaller than the previously added distance last_d1 (the last update in the current Pareto Front). Indeed, last_d1 is associated with a smaller M2 distance last_d2 (not explicitly handled in the algorithm but actually the last updated index, the previous $d2$), so the order $\text{last_d2} < d2$ implies that $(\text{last_d1}, \text{last_d2})$ and $(d1, d2)$ are both not dominated, and both appear in the current Pareto front.

When our algorithm terminates, the `results` array contains, for each node n and each iteration, all the best distances of paths from the source towards any n . Now we explain how to answer the 2COP+ problem from there. For each destination n , for all stricter sub-constraints $c0' \leq c0$, $c1' \leq c1$ and $c2' \leq c2$, we have:

- $f(n, c0', c1', c2', 2)$, i.e., the paths to n that respect all constraint and optimizes M2, is the first element in $\text{dist}[n][c0' - 1]$ (as they were discovered before the $c0^{\text{th}}$ iteration) that verifies constraints $c1'$ and $c2'$ (as they are indexed on M2, the first feasible path is also the path optimizing M2).
- $f(n, c0', c1', c2', 1)$ is the last element in $\text{dist}[n][c0' - 1]$ that verifies constraints $c1'$ and $c2'$. Indeed, to be on the Pareto front on the iteration, each path with a higher $d1$ must have a lower $d2$. Thus, as $d2$ serves as its index, the path that optimized M1 is the last element of the array.
- to compute $f(n, c0', c1', c2', 0)$, let first denote k the smallest integer such that $\text{dist}[n][k]$ contains an element that verifies constraints $c1'$ and $c2'$.
 $f(n, c0', c1', c2', 0)$ is any of such elements in $\text{dist}[n][k]$.

As one might have noticed, to keep our data structure simple, computing $f(n, c0', c1', c2', Mj)$, $j = 0, 1, 2$ is not exactly done in constant time. Indeed, we may have to search an element in an ordered list of size Γ at worst and, when $i = 0$, do this $\log(\text{SEGMAX})$ times to find the smallest k having such element. For a formal solution, we could modify our

data structure to convert the list representing the Pareto front into several static arrays giving efficiently the solution.

Complexity. The overall time complexity of BEST2COP is:

$$O(\text{SEGMAX} \times |E'| \times \Gamma)$$

This complexity is clearly visible with the four nested loops in the `ExtendPaths` procedure. In the worst-case extendable is of size $|V|$, and for each node, we iterate over all the edges of its successor. Hence those three “for” loops, in the worst case, iterate over all the edges in E' . For the fourth “for” loop, the size of `d_list` (the number of extendable paths for a given node) is at most Γ , by design. Procedure `ExtendPaths` is called at most `SEGMAX` times, hence the given complexity.

G' being a complete multigraph, we know that $|E'| \geq |V|^2$. In fact, an important parameter is L , the average number of links between a pair of nodes, $L = \frac{|E'|}{|V|^2}$. The complexity can then be rewritten as $O(\text{SEGMAX} \times |V|^2 \times L \times \Gamma)$. In practice, in particular for the evaluations, we will consider that:

- $\text{SEGMAX} = 10$ as it is close to the real hardware limit;
- $L = 2$: while some pairs of nodes may have more than two parallel links connecting them in G , we argue that, in average in G' , one can expect that the total number of links in E' is lower than $2|V|^2$. Indeed, while one node and several adjacency segments can co-exist for a given pair (u, v) in E' , adjacency segments are not likely to be numerous within transformed graphs (they tend to either be dominated by the node segment or dominated by another adjacency one);
- $\Gamma = 1000$: while this value is controllable to reflect the expected product trueness-constraint on M2, we consider a trueness level t of 10 (for a 0.1ms accuracy) regarding a maximal constraint $c_2 = 100\text{ms}$.

The last variable is the most sensitive as, although like others it has only a linear impact on the complexity, it can grow fast according to the necessary/expected accuracy of one-way propagation delay measurements. In fact, if Γ is very high due to extra-fine grain accuracy of measurements (e.g., sub-microsecond trueness), $\text{dist}[n]$ can be converted to a hashmap instead of an array. Indeed, doing so, the memory usage of $\text{dist}[n]$ would not depend on Γ but rather on the size of the Pareto front (that we expect to be lower than the M2 theoretical spreading thanks to a limited amount of distinct distances), at the cost of a slightly slower insertion, and memory access, which will depend on the number of distinct distances (but not directly on the spreading).

4 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the performance of BEST2COP through several evaluation methods, ranging from purely virtual worst-cases to practical cases with real topologies and

valuations. We show not only that BEST2COP can easily deal with realistic cases in less than half a second in worst cases, but also that, when not verifying any graph based assumptions (just setting $\Gamma \leq 1000$ and an average of two parallel links, *i.e.*, $L = 2$, with a full iteration space visit) BEST2COP never takes more than one minute. Conversely to most evaluations regarding QoS Routing algorithms, we focus on worst-case results. To do so, in the set-ups aforementioned, **we will not use constraints to our advantages, *i.e.*, we will not prune paths** except in the appendix. Ignoring constraints from the problem may seem easier at first. However, with pseudo infinite constraints, no path distances can be pruned to reduce the exploration space, leading to a fast-growing pareto-front which stresses our solution as much as possible. For all the evaluations, we rely on a 4,2 GHz Intel Core i7 CPU. However, we do not exploit multiple cores as we show here only results with a purely sequential approach. Finally, the code will be made available if our submission is accepted.

4.1 Forcing BEST2COP to explore its full iteration space

We first show that BEST2COP *can not* exceed an execution time of one minute. To do so, we virtually fill the data structures of our algorithms as quickly as a purely theoretical SR graph with $|V|$ nodes with 2 parallel links between each node would allow. More formally, at iteration i , we force each node to extend $i \times S$ paths (*i.e.*, the maximum number of paths possible at this iteration) with the 2 segments reaching every other $|V| - 1$ nodes, resulting in $i \times S \times 2 \times |V|$ operations for each extensible node at each iteration. We study the execution time of BEST2COP for $\Gamma = \{100, 500, 1000\}$ and $|V|$ ranging from 100 to 1000. Since it is impossible for BEST2COP to perform more operations than in this set-up, it gives us the worst possible time for BEST2COP on any topology of $|V|$ nodes and two parallel links on average. Note that we do not actually follow a concrete topology, *i.e.*, it is not proven that there exists one for it.

Figure 3 shows the results for this extreme analysis. BEST2COP's execution time never exceeds one minute in all the space we explore (up to 1000 nodes topologies). Besides, its performance is quadratic with respect to the number of nodes as detailed in the previous section. Γ plays an important role in BEST2COP's execution time, as it dictates here the ultimate size of the pareto front. While, as stated in Section 2, $\Gamma = 1000$ is arguably enough to capture the extent of the metrics' valuation when its trueness is taken into account, it is ultimately tunable. Thus, a value of 500, 100 or even less may very well suffice depending on S_1 , S_2 , and the desired constraints. The fact that Γ is tunable and likely to be small in practical scenario is of great importance, as one can see that BEST2COP already always stays below 10

Figure 3: BEST2COP's performance (s) regarding the number of nodes ($|V|$) for $\Gamma = \{100, 500, 1000\}$ when making it perform the maximum number of operations if $L = 2$. While the results depend on Γ which is tunable, BEST2COP scales well and always remains under one minute at worst.

seconds with $\Gamma = 100$ (e.g., with small constraints). Even with worst cases, BEST2COP shows promising results and a manageable worst possible time. However, this evaluation remains purely virtual and not very representative, as we do not follow any graph structure or any weights to guide our algorithms.

4.2 SR Graph with Random Valuation

While the previous section dealt with unrealistic worst times, we show here a fairer, average case. We already explained that an SR Graph G' will always be (at least) a full mesh when the original graph is connected regardless of the original topology. We use this convenient property to easily create sets of SR graph, with which we will evaluate the performance of BEST2COP.

We generate complete graphs of $|V|$ nodes and more than $|V|^2$ edges. To emulate adjacency segments, we add an additional link between every node, creating so a *double full-mesh* graph. One additional link looks enough, as realistic topologies tend to possess a low number of adjacency segments once converted (< 10 for 1000 nodes). Regarding IGP costs (M1), we chose weights uniformly at random between 1 and $2^{31}/10$, which is higher than the maximum IGP weights possible with current protocols.

We evaluate the performances with three spreading values $S = \{50, 100, 500\}$. We perform these tests for $|V|$ ranging from 100 to 1000. To account for the randomness of the weights, we generate, for each $|V|$, 30 differently weighted distinct random topologies, and run BEST2COP on $|V| \times 0.1$ nodes as source. While this evaluation is fairer than the

Figure 4: BEST2COP worst-case when considering randomly weighted SR graphs with three spreading valuations. BEST2COP remains always under the second and scales decently regarding $|V|$.

previous one, it is still far from advantageous for our analysis, as we do not benefit from pattern generated by realistic delays. The times obtained are shown in Figure 4.

One can see that, on this evaluation based on random weights, BEST2COP stays under one second in all of its runs. Again, BEST2COP scales quite efficiently with the dimension of the network (quadratic in $|V|$). It is also worth noticing that a S_2 value of 500 leads to the worst time results, while a value of 1000 or only 100 leading to respectively a slightly better or a very notable decrease in execution time. This can be explained through the value taken by S_2 in each experiment regarding $\Gamma = 1000$. When $S_2 = 100$, which is the best-case scenario, the first iterations of our algorithms have a small pareto front that is limited by $i \times S_2 < \Gamma$ in particular for small i . With larger weights, the spreading of distances comes faster but only at some extents. Indeed, after a value S_2 greater than 700 (see the inflection point at 700 in Fig. 7 in the appendix), the number of paths that are not explored increases, because their distances are greater than the constraints. This means we can benefit from having a large spreading. Due to the latter, many paths within the network are bound to have a delay higher than 1000. Since we consider paths with a delay over 1000 to be unusable, we ignore a lot of path and edges, and thus end up with a very fast execution time, less than a second in any random cases for any tested sources.

A too large spreading leads to more pruned paths, which in turn leads to low execution times as well. In addition, we considered SR graphs that were not constructed through the translation of an existing topology. BEST2COP can also benefit from real raw networks' structures and weights. Indeed, the SR graph translated from a real topology is likely to be

Figure 5: BEST2COP's performances on realistic topologies with realistic weights (but random delays for ISP1). Execution times remain mostly under 100ms, even though some of the delays are still randomized for ISP1.

vastly simpler, not only considering its number of edges, but also the valuation of its metrics should be more sparse.

4.3 Towards more Realistic Scenarios

The previous section was aimed at showing BEST2COP's performances at worst, or in random, non-advantageous scenarios. In this section, we show BEST2COP performance in more realistic scenarios. We still do not prune any paths and keep the largest constraint settings we can with $\Gamma = 1000$. First, we evaluate BEST2COP's performance on real network's topologies with real IGP cost but random delays. Then, we use real network structures, complete but smaller, with real IGP costs and delays. BEST2COP indeed benefits from concrete characteristics, making it an efficient and deployable solution for real-life cases.

We first use the network structure of a large ISP, denoted ISP1, which consists of about 1200 nodes and 3000 edges. While we do possess the IGP costs of each link, we do not have their delays. Thus, we once again use random values, but not in the SR Graph. We consider the worst spreading we found experimentally for w_{2G} (i.e., leading to the worst computing time, see Section A.2 in the appendix for the detailed analysis), $S_2 = \{70\}$, with S_2 denoting the spreading in G . We also consider two other real ISP networks, namely ISP2 and ISP3 with real valuations both for M1 and M2. The results are shown in Figure 5 as a violin plot, whose widths represents the number of executions that took the time shown on the y-axis, in ms.

One can see that BEST2COP indeed benefits from the realistic properties, as it now rarely exceeds 75ms in the most disadvantageous experiments. The execution times were greatly enhanced thanks to the realistic structure and weights. However, while we already went from a few hundreds of milliseconds to a few dozens at most by simply using real topologies and IGP weights, the most sensitive parameters, the delay, is still random for ISP1, our largest almost real case. Thus, although BEST2COP shows very great execution times, real-life delays on smaller topologies (ISP2 and ISP3) are even easier patterns that BEST2COP can solve in a negligible amount of time and for which Γ and the accuracy can be then enlarged.

5 RELATED WORK

QoS routing and TE problems have attracted a lot of interest [14, 16, 24, 30]. Due to their complexity, most of the proposed solutions are approximations or heuristics [19]. A large amount of the proposed algorithms rely on the computation of a single metric that combines linearly the ones that have to be taken into account, then running a shortest-path algorithm to find the solution [3, 11, 21, 22]. Other solutions use a k -shortest path approach along with a non-linear cost function [7, 31]. Lagrangian-based algorithms (using the Dijkstra algorithm) are especially popular and can be extended (at a cost) to reach the optimal solution [23]. The performance and results of this kind of solutions rely on various parameters that may be hard to tune [4]. On the other hand, we propose a simple algorithm whose guaranteed worst-case complexity relies solely on pre-existing network characteristics and is fitted for real-time routing decisions.

Some algorithms do not rely on aggregated metrics. [26] selects paths by weighting the trade-off between the time complexity and quality of solution. A*Prune [12] find multiple shortest path that satisfy the constraints by pruning paths that are not promising. Closer to our work, Chen et al. [5] showed that MCP remains polynomial as long as $m - 1$ metrics are bounded. They thus discretize the metric space of $m - 1$ metric and solve the problem through an Extended Bellman-Ford or extended Dijkstra algorithm [33]. We bridge the gap to a real but exact SR implementation.

More specific to DCLC, DCUR [27] explores the network by extending paths either through the least-delay or the least-cost path. DCUR has been combined with Bellman Ford to create DCBF [34], which guesses promising paths through an estimated cost. Closer to our work, Constrained Bellman-Ford [32], solves DCLC exactly by exploring paths in a greedy fashion through a priority queue indexed on their delay. Their worst-case running time is however exponential wrt the network size, requiring ϵ -optimal approximations.

Other works investigated TE with segment routing. In [6], Cianfrani et al. propose a solution to compute the minimal number of segments to support a given QoS request. While [17] provides a language to express constraints for SR and a resolution algorithm relying on constraint programming, Gay et al. [15] further improves the computation times for such SR paths. Our work comes with several advantages, simplicity being its main strength. Our approach is an exact algorithm with a straight-forward worst-case time complexity, with no parameters requiring tuning. Our algorithm is also centered around a state-of-the-art TE technology. While other works usually detach path computations and their deployment, we are, to the best of our knowledge, the first ones to propose an algorithm that leverages and takes into account SR deployment constraints. In addition, we provide extensive evaluations which bound the worst-case time complexity of BEST2COP for the challenging 2COP+ problem.

6 CONCLUSION

While management overhead lead to a QoS winter in the past decade, Segment Routing marked its rebirth, and with it, the need for practical solution to the DCLC problem. In this paper, we proposed an easy, exact and efficient algorithm, adapted for SR-aware network, and that leverage both SR operational constraints and the trueness of the delay to reach a worst-case time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(|V|^2)$. Our algorithm, BEST2COP is able to optimize any of the three constraints (cost, delay and number of segments) and can handle both realistic and worst case scenarios through simple, adaptive and efficient structures. We showed through extensive experimentation that we deal efficiently with realistic cases, and that, at worst, the time taken by BEST2COP remains manageable.

We believe BEST2COP is already mature and simple enough to be implemented and deployed in real ISP in a near future. We also envision to improve BEST2COP and conduct many studies to both enhance our contribution to better understand the theoretical challenges we face with SR TE. First, BEST2COP can be improved through smart strategy for cache reuse and by exploiting its parallelizable nature. Second, we aim to look for other structures (like hashmaps) to handle cases where Γ requires to be enlarged because of really high trueness requirements. Third, based on this observation, we aim to study in depth the impact of graph characteristics on our performance.

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APPENDIX

A ADDITIONAL RESULTS

A.1 Effects of the Metric Spreading

Figure 6 shows the impact of the maximum value of the metric on G (the non-transformed graph) on the execution time. This experiment was done on the ISP-1 topology and allowed used to extract the worst calibration for our experiments. We varied max metric (the upper bound of the random selection of the delay) from 10 to 1000, focusing on 10 to 100. One can see that, at first, the execution time increases with max

Figure 6: BEST2COP performance on ISP-1 depending on the max weight s in E when adding random delays. The execution times increase with max metrics, as our structures fill up more quickly. However, past a certain point, the pruning of the links with a weight above Γ greatly enhance the performances.

metric. As more values can appear on each link, the number of collision on $M2$ diminishes and thus our structures (indexed on $M2$) fill up more quickly with more paths to extend, leading to a higher execution time (from 75ms for max metric = 10 to ≈ 200 for max metric = 70). However, after a certain point (namely, max metric = 70), execution time diminish. Indeed, as the maximum value of the metric rises, the number of paths violating our maximum constraint $\Gamma = 1000$ increases as well, leading to more and more pruned paths and thus better execution time. In summary, while more diverse weights fill up our data structure quickly, this effect is then counterbalanced by the pruning of the paths, as their maximum weight increases as well.

Similarly to Figure 6, Figure 7 shows the impact of the spreading S_2 on BEST2COP performance, on randomly weighted SR graph. Note that conversely to Figure 6, we consider here the maximum value of the metric on G' . A similar phenomenon can be seen here, as the execution time increases with S_2 until reaching a peak at 700 for an average time of about 900ms, before decreasing to 800ms for a spread of 1000. Past this peak, the effects of the pruning of paths violation our maximum constraint on $c2$ (1000) can be seen, as BEST2COP executes slightly faster.

A.2 Effects of the Constraints to Look at the Computing Time

As mentioned several times, all of the times shown above did not use realistic constraints, and thus prevented us to prune paths during the execution to reduce the exploration space.

Figure 7: BEST2COP performance on random SR graphs depending on S_2 . Once again, the execution times increase with S_2 , as our structures fill up more quickly. The effect of the pruning can be seen starting an S_2 of 700.

Figure 8: BEST2COP time with respect to the constraint on $c2$, on ISP-1.

In reality, ISPs would most likely have strict constraints on delays (≈ 2 to 20ms), allowing BEST2COP to ignore a large amount of path that it would otherwise explore. In this section, we show that, when considering constraints, BEST2COP exhibits very good execution time to find a path that respects the constraint towards every other node. To do so, we retrieve the randomly valuated SR Graph than lead to the worst execution time in the experiments described in Section 4.2 (Figure 4). We then run BEST2COP, adding a constraint $c2$ ranging from 1ms up to 100ms. The results are shown in Figure 9. We see that the ability to pruned path enhances our performances, lead to sub-millisecond execution time for strict constraints. As the constraints grows larger, less paths are pruned and the execution time increases. However, once the constraint reaches a point where no path can be pruned, our performance get stable again. In practice, if we do not aim at solving the optimization problem but rather the decision one, we can expect execution times to drop as feasible paths get easier to find.

Figure 9: BEST2COP time with respect to the constraint on c_2 , on a random SR graph.

A.3 Playing with Constraints: Necessary Number of Segments

Here we are interested in the number of segments related to a given constraint and how the SEGMAX limit affect the exactitude (completeness) of the SR technique. Admittedly, we can only claim the exactness of BEST2COP in a Segment Routing context, as we do not explore paths that would require more than SEGMAX segments. We only explore *SR-feasible paths* that respects c_0 , and thus may miss paths respecting c_2 due to SR’s operational constraints. In this section, we explore the exactitude of BEST2COP in the general case, putting SR aside. In other words, we aim at studying if c_0 is too restrictive when trying to compute multi-constrained paths, *i.e.*, if SR *hides* feasible solutions. To do so, we do not stop the algorithm after SEGMAX iterations, but let it run until there is no path left to explore. We keep, for each source the number of iterations (*i.e.*, the number of required segments) necessary to explore non-dominated path towards all other nodes. We perform this evaluation on the real topologies studied in Section 4. The results are shown in Figures 10 for constraints of 5, 10, 50, and 100 ms. The unlabeled bar show destination for which no solution were found.

We can see that in many cases, a low number of segments is required, especially if the constraint is loose enough. Note that here we look for the optimal path that may require more segment hops than just a feasible one verifying the delay constraint. We can relax that to only verify the c_2 constraint and show that a path segment of less than SEGMAX exist in most situations and can show better performances. In summary, in practice, once constraints are loose enough to

Figure 10: Distribution of the number of necessary TE segments depending on the source for our largest realistic topology on four constraints. It shows the minimal number of iterations to find every non-dominated paths towards a given node. While, for most destinations, every non-dominated path was listed before SEGMAX iteration, for some strict c_2 constraints, it can require more than SEGMAX to claim the optimal exactitude.

find paths, the latter will be found in almost always less than 10 iteration. However, a small minority are left unexplored.